

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.9

Software for improved procedures for rapid mapping of earthquake shaking, including adjustment factors for local site effects (RRE)

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EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
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BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
BN	Bayesian Network
GMICE	Ground Motion Intensity Conversion Equation
GMM	Ground Motion Model
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration

INDEX OF CONTENTS

Document revision history	1
List of partners.....	2
Glossary.....	2
Index of contents	1
Index of figures.....	1
Index of TABLEs.....	2
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
2 PYTHON CODE FOR THE GENERATION OF SHAKE-MAPS	2
2.1 Structure of the code.....	2
2.2 Input data.....	3
2.2.1 ‘Static’ data.....	3
2.2.1.1 Parameter file.....	3
2.2.1.2 List of stations	5
2.2.1.3 Map of site effects	5
2.2.1.4 Conversion table for amplification factors	6
2.2.2 ‘Dynamic’ data	6
2.2.2.1 Input file for felt reports	6
2.2.2.2 Input file for earthquake event.....	7
2.2.2.3 Input file for station recordings	8
2.3 Output data	9
2.4 Flexibility and extension	11

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 1-1: Overview of the Bayesian code for the generation of shake-maps.....	1
Figure 2-1: Structure of the Python files required for shake-map computation.	2
Figure 2-2: Extract of the file containing the list of stations.	5
Figure 2-3: Extract of the file containing the site effects.	6
Figure 2-4: Extract of the file containing the conversion table.	6
Figure 2-5: Extract of the file containing information on felt reports.	7
Figure 2-6: Extract of the earthquake event file.	8
Figure 2-7: Extract of the event data file containing peak strong-motion parameters from the seismic stations.	8
Figure 2-8: Extract of the output txt file for PGA. Four columns are present: latitude, longitude, mean PGA [%g], $\sigma_{\log 10 \text{PGA}}$	9
Figure 2-9: Extract of the output txt file for macroseismic intensity. Three columns are present: latitude, longitude, mean intensity.....	9

Figure 2-10: PGA shake-map 10
Figure 2-11: Macroseismic intensity shake-map 10

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 2-1: List of options and fields in the xml parameter file 3

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This brief technical report details the code and data structure of the software that has been developed by BRGM for the derivation of shake-maps (see Figure 1-1), to be used in the TURNkey platform. The software has the following features:

- generation of shake-maps for PGA and macroseismic intensity;
- use of strong-motion measures from seismic stations and felt reports as sources of observation;
- integration of site effects through amplification factors;
- parametrisation of the computation (choice of map extent, computation grid, GMM and GMICE models, etc.).

Posterior distributions of PGA and intensity at grid points, in XYZ format

Figure 1-1: Overview of the Bayesian code for the generation of shake-maps

2 PYTHON CODE FOR THE GENERATION OF SHAKE-MAPS

The Bayesian approach for the derivation of shake-maps has been developed by BRGM as a Python code, which is detailed in the following sub-sections. The computation process is illustrated through a shake-map implementation in TB-2 (Pyrenees area), specifically the M 4.3 Lourdes earthquake of 30th December 2012.

2.1 Structure of the code

Figure 2-1: Structure of the Python files required for shake-map computation.

2.2 Input data

2.2.1 'Static' data

2.2.1.1 Parameter file

The shake-map algorithm is controlled by a parameter file, in .xml format (e.g., '*ParametresTapiaPyr.xml*'). The fields described in Table 2-1 can be modified by the user (default values are indicated in the table).

Table 2-1: List of options and fields in the xml parameter file.

Element	Fields	Description
GMPE choix	choice among "Tapia2006", "AkkarBoomer2007", "AkkarBoomer2010", "Chiou2008"	which GMM to use
GMICE choix	choice among "GMICECaprioetal2015", "GMICESouriau2006"	which GMICE to use
file_mmi name	"mini_test_mmi.json" (file name)	input file for felt reports
Files_ES stationlist	"statlist_Pyr_mod.txt" (file name)	list of stations from which to use seismic recordings (created by the user)
Files_ES xyz_ES	"sispyr.xyz" (file name)	map of site effects, in terms of soil classes
Files_ES EStableFile	"EStable_Pyr.txt" (file name)	conversion table for amplification factors
Params_ES stationlist_format	"zone_code" if stations list contains site effect zone codes "zone_coeff" if stations list contains site effect coefficients directly	-
Params_ES pgalim	"200" (number)	acceleration threshold (in cm/s ²) above which to apply different amplification factors (see conversion table);
Params_ES ProjSite	"epsg:3035" (EPSG format)	projection system for the site effects map
Selec_Sta funcIsInZone	if "IsInBox" then enter coordinates of the box corners, or expression using boundaries of site effect map if "IsInSispyr", CornersIsInZone are not used	selection of stations where site effects can be determined
CornersIsInZone	"[np.min(Lon_ES), np.max(Lon_ES), np.min(Lat_ES), np.max(Lat_ES)]" (either numbers or expression)	definition of boundaries of the box
Calc_Grid option_mapping	if "bounding_box" define [lon_min,lon_max,lat_min,lat_max] in WGS84 format	spatial extent of the shake-map

	if "epicenter_centered" the map is automatically centred around the epicentre	
Calc_Grid bounding_box_pts	"[-1,0.75,42.25,43.75]"	manual definition of the bounding box of the computation grid
Calc_Grid map_verif	"1" (0 or 1)	to check calculation of grid points
Width value	"1.7" (number)	if option_mapping = "epicenter_centered", define Width (EW direction) of the grid (in decimal degrees)
Height value	"1.7" (number)	if option_mapping = "epicenter_centered", define Height (NS direction) of the grid (in decimal degrees)
Wx value	"48" (integer number)	number of grid points in the EW direction
Wy value	"48" (integer number)	number of grid points in the NS direction
Nbr_Subdivisionx value	"8" (integer number)	number of sub-grids in the EW direction
Nbr_Subdivisiony value	"8" (integer number)	number of sub-grids in the NS direction
Lenx value	"500" (integer number)	number of points in the EW direction for the display grid (interpolation from the computation grid)
Leny value	"500" (integer number)	number of points in the NS direction for the display grid (interpolation from the computation grid)
corrDist value	"13.5" (number)	distance (in km) for the spatial correlation model, in the functional form: $\rho = \exp(-3*d/corrDist)$, where d is the distance between two points
facteurmmi1 value	"1" (number)	reduce this value to increase the weight of felt reports in the shake-map ($\sigma_{MMI1} = 0.7 * \text{facteurmmi1}$)
facteurmmi2 value	"1" (number)	reduce this value to increase the weight of felt reports in the shake-map ($\sigma_{MMI2} = 1.4 * \text{facteurmmi2}$)
alpha1 value	"2.27"	coefficient of the GMICE (1 st branch)
beta1 value	"1.647" (number)	coefficient of the GMICE (1 st branch)
alpha2 value	"-1.361" (number)	coefficient of the GMICE (2 nd branch)
beta2 value	"3.822" (number)	coefficient of the GMICE (2 nd branch)
mmi_lim value	"4.9052" (number)	intensity threshold above which to apply the 2 nd branch
Function_influence value	"0" (0 or 1)	if Function_influence = "1" and if the observation distance $\text{distVal } i > \text{Distance_influence}$ then $\sigma_{Eta}[i] =$

		$\sigma_{\text{Eta}[i]}^*$ $\exp(\text{distVal}/\text{Distance_influence})$
Distance_influence value	"50" (number)	value of the influence distance in km

2.2.1.2 List of stations

This file (see Figure 2-2) declares the stations in the area that can be used to collect seismic recordings: this file must be created by the used in order to specify which station may be used as observations for the shake-map, and also to provide information on the soil conditions at the stations. It contains the following fields:

- “Lat”, “Lon”: coordinates of the station (in decimal degrees, EPSG:4326);
- “Code”: name of the station;
- “Vel”: code for the site conditions of the station (to be used by the conversion table);
- “Network”: network to which the station belongs (not used);
- “Description”: type of station (not used).


```

"Lat", "Lon", "Code", "Vel", "Network", "Description"
42.434553, 1.533475, ARBS, 7, CA, BB
43.0858, -0.7003, ATE, 7, FR, BB
41.84381, 1.96546, AVIN, 6, CA, ACC
42.707643, 0.818132, CARA, 7, CA, BB
41.88158, 0.7506, CAVN, 7, CA, BB
42.255628, 2.67579, CBEU, 7, CA, BB
42.284413, 2.178993, CBRU, 7, CA, BB
41.882878, 2.904135, CCAS, 6, CA, BB
41.6896, 2.4923, CELS, 6, CA, ACC
42.598657, 1.254057, CEST, 7, CA, BB
41.761172, 2.434567, CFON, 7, CA, BB
42.478108, 1.972967, CLLI, 7, CA, BB
42.229097, 1.316527, CORG, 7, CA, BB
41.9724, 2.0488, CORI, 7, CA, BB
42.310538, 3.162432, CPAL, 6, CA, BB
42.374433, 1.132737, CSOR, 7, CA, BB
42.322278, 0.77235, CTRE, 7, CA, BB
43.2197, -1.5071, EALK, 7, ES, BB
  
```

Figure 2-2: Extract of the file containing the list of stations.

2.2.1.3 Map of site effects

This file (see Figure 2-3) contains codes that represent site conditions in the area. It is in X,Y,Z format with 3 columns:

- 1st column: X coordinates in the projected system (in metres, EPSG:3035 in the present example);
- 2nd column: Y coordinates in the projected system;
- 3rd column: code value.

Site Code	Value	Category
3321807.49266	2372423.58434	7
3322307.49266	2372423.58434	7
3322807.49266	2372423.58434	7
3323307.49266	2372423.58434	7
3323807.49266	2372423.58434	7
3324307.49266	2372423.58434	7
3324807.49266	2372423.58434	7
3325307.49266	2372423.58434	7
3325807.49266	2372423.58434	7
3326307.49266	2372423.58434	7
3326807.49266	2372423.58434	7
3327307.49266	2372423.58434	7
3327807.49266	2372423.58434	7

Figure 2-3: Extract of the file containing the site effects.

2.2.1.4 Conversion table for amplification factors

This file (see Figure 2-4) contains a conversion table that links the site codes for the site effects map to amplification factors (to be directly multiplied to the acceleration at rock conditions): in the present case, the amplification are specific to the studied area (i.e., ad-hoc values calibrated for this specific area), but it is also possible to build a table of amplification factors using the EC8 classification. It contains the following fields:

- “Condition_ES”: site code value;
- “CoefESinf200”: multiplicative factor to apply (for lower acceleration values, by default the threshold is 200 cm/s²);
- “CoefESsup200”: multiplicative factor to apply (for higher acceleration values, by default the threshold is 200 cm/s²).

Condition_ES	CoefESinf200	CoefESsup200
2	1.8	1.35
3	1.6	1.2
4	1.5	1.17
5	1.2	1.0
6	1.35	1.15
7	1.0	1.0
9	0.0	0.0

Figure 2-4: Extract of the file containing the conversion table.

2.2.2 ‘Dynamic’ data

2.2.2.1 Input file for felt reports

In TB-2, felt reports are obtained from the BCSF website (www.franceisme.fr), in JSON format (see Figure 2-5). The fields that are required by the code are: “coordinates” and “intensity”.

```

mini_test_mmi.json X
{
  "type": "FeatureCollection",
  "created": 1581343233,
  "nbresp": 1,
  "input_date": "2012-12-30T23:35:00",
  "features": [
    {
      "id": "DYFI.2425",
      "type": "Feature",
      "geometry": {
        "type": "Point",
        "coordinates": [
          0.99,
          42.93
        ]
      },
      "properties": {
        "intensity": 1,
        "channels": [],
        "name": "ARGEIN (1 responses)",
        "instrumentType": "BCSF",
        "commType": "DIG",
        "location": "",
        "network": "INTENSITY",
        "intensity_flag": "",
        "station_type": "macroseismic",
        "code": "2425",
        "source": "BCSF (EMS98)"
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-5: Extract of the file containing information on felt reports.

2.2.2.2 Input file for earthquake event

An event.xml file (see Figure 2-6) is generated by SeisComp3 following the detection of an event, and this file is then used to extract the characteristics of the event. The fields that are required by the code are: “lat”, “lon”, “mag” and “depth”.

```

event.xml * X
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<!DOCTYPE earthquake SYSTEM "earthquake.dtd">
<earthquake id="1356910603"
lat="43.1600"
lon="-0.1700"
mag="4.3"
year="2012"
month="12"
day="30"
hour="23"
minute="35"
second="00"
timezone="GMT"
depth="10"
network=""
locstring="E NAY.FRA"
created="1358163691" />

```

Figure 2-6: Extract of the earthquake event file.

2.2.2.3 Input file for station recordings

An event_dat.xml file (see Figure 2-7) is generated by SeisComp3 following the detection of an event, and this file is then used to extract the measurements from the seismic stations (Acc. In %, PGV in cm/s). The code only uses the values from the horizontal components:

- if only one horizontal component is present, this single value is taken as an observation;
- if both horizontal components are present, the geometric mean of both values is taken as an observation.

```

event_dat.xml X
<station code="URDF" name="URDF" insttype="Sispyr" lat="43.43830" lon="-0.59310" dist="46.151690"
<comp name="HHE">
<acc value="0.0960" flag="0" />
<vel value="0.0343" flag="0" />
<psa03 value="0.1057" flag="0" />
<psa10 value="0.0233" flag="0" />
<psa30 value="0.0019" flag="0" />
</comp>
<comp name="HHZ">
<acc value="0.0000" flag="0" />
<vel value="0.0000" flag="0" />
<psa03 value="0.0000" flag="0" />
<psa10 value="0.0000" flag="0" />
<psa30 value="0.0000" flag="0" />
</comp>
<comp name="HHN">
<acc value="0.0851" flag="0" />
<vel value="0.0225" flag="0" />
<psa03 value="0.1107" flag="0" />
<psa10 value="0.0190" flag="0" />
<psa30 value="0.0019" flag="0" />
</comp>
</station>

```

Figure 2-7: Extract of the event data file containing peak strong-motion parameters from the seismic stations.

2.3 Output data

The Python code is tested on a historical event of TB-2, namely the M 4.3 Lourdes earthquake of 30th December 2012. A total of 41 strong-motion measurements from stations and 105 felt reports have been used in order to generate the shake-map: raw outputs of the code consist of text files (see Figure 2-8 and Figure 2-9) for PGA (in %g) and macroseismic intensity on the display grid (interpolated from the computation grid, and accounting for site effects in the area). Shake-maps, containing mean values and related uncertainties, may then be plotted, as shown in Figure 2-10 and Figure 2-11.

Latitude	Longitude	Mean PGA [%g]	$\sigma_{\log 10 \text{PGA}}$
42.90917103988795	0.09211711836599945	0.7314493560015283	0.40123942049442707
42.90917103988795	0.09662309642384659	0.7372141538480101	0.4015588836618801
42.90917103988795	0.10112907448169395	0.6706751053170491	0.4018201885003125
42.90917103988795	0.10563505253954109	0.6383456430809268	0.4020387510411966
42.90917103988795	0.11014103059738845	0.6659860030814305	0.4022284201568386
42.90917103988795	0.11464700865523558	0.6663106935142207	0.40237424454483445
42.90917103988795	0.11915298671308294	0.6383755874477471	0.4025318037276023
42.90917103988795	0.12365896477093008	0.636217349548429	0.4026863641555097
42.90917103988795	0.12816494282877744	0.6449529164523216	0.4028387908300438
42.90917103988795	0.13267092088662458	0.6432935408732705	0.4029955288101776
42.90917103988795	0.13717689894447194	0.47760167168377865	0.4031449078898159
42.90917103988795	0.14168287700231907	0.32899589859387945	0.4032893186056873
42.90917103988795	0.14618885506016643	0.3292220933829781	0.40342556885345215
42.90917103988795	0.15069483311801357	0.37096608490446087	0.4035524985871077
42.90917103988795	0.15520081117586093	0.5866206968036237	0.40366796389927334
42.90917103988795	0.15970678923370807	0.6409013987692964	0.4037801233618741

Figure 2-8: Extract of the output txt file for PGA. Four columns are present: latitude, longitude, mean PGA [%g], $\sigma_{\log 10 \text{PGA}}$.

Latitude	Longitude	Mean Intensity
42.90917103988795	0.09211711836599945	3.6909281252965433
42.90917103988795	0.09662309642384659	3.70058097354104
42.90917103988795	0.10112907448169395	3.6113614203705615
42.90917103988795	0.10563505253954109	3.5712993269465394
42.90917103988795	0.11014103059738845	3.60811886282427
42.90917103988795	0.11464700865523558	3.6141226312797556
42.90917103988795	0.11915298671308294	3.5778672922032153
42.90917103988795	0.12365896477093008	3.5789198278503047
42.90917103988795	0.12816494282877744	3.597538749982189
42.90917103988795	0.13267092088662458	3.6000818850788128
42.90917103988795	0.13717689894447194	3.341549897342988
42.90917103988795	0.14168287700231907	3.1221305466242106
42.90917103988795	0.14618885506016643	3.1211016613256923
42.90917103988795	0.15069483311801357	3.182596361262813
42.90917103988795	0.15520081117586093	3.5105132424570815
42.90917103988795	0.15970678923370807	3.5953585606093097

Figure 2-9: Extract of the output txt file for macroseismic intensity. Three columns are present: latitude, longitude, mean intensity.

Figure 2-10: PGA shake-map.

Figure 2-11: Macro seismic intensity shake-map.

2.4 Flexibility and extension

The code in its present form has been specifically designed to generate shake-maps for the TB-2 (Pyrénées). However, the code has been developed so that some degree of flexibility is available when implementing the code for other TB areas:

- “Static data” files can easily be developed for other areas than TB-2 (site classification map, list of stations, etc.).
- The spatial extent of the shake-map (and the resolution of the grid) may be configured to fit any geographical area.
- “Dynamic data” files (generated by SeisComp3) may be processed by the shake-map code, independent of the location of the earthquake.
- There is a limited choice of GMM or GMICE to be applied when deriving the shake-map.
- There is an option to account for felt reports, in addition to seismic recordings.
- The site classification map may be expressed in different coordinate projection systems, as long as they are in EPSG format.

However, further customisation and additional features may be added to the code:

- Extension of the code to include the OpenQuake GMM library and the USGS ShakeMap® GMICE library: Python classes for GMM and GMICE models have already been created in the Bayesian shake-map code, therefore the connection to OpenQuake and USGS ShakeMap® libraries (which are both based on Python language) are possible with limited efforts.
- Extension of the code to generate shake-maps with different intensity measures (e.g., SA(T), PGV): this feature has already been demonstrated in the Matlab version of the code, which was shared with the platform developers.
- Generation of EMS-98 intensity maps: the choice of macroseismic scale depends on the type of GMICE that is used (e.g., the use of European GMICE provides intensities on the EMS98 scale).
- For now, the Bayesian shake-map code uses grid maps (in XYZ format) of site classes, which are then translated to amplification factors. More flexibility is needed on this aspect, in order to also use maps expressed as Vs30. However, further developments are required in the pre-treatment stage of the code in order to achieve this.